

"New Technologies in Archaeology" course: Questionnaire

 Anonymous – no personal information is collected.

 Voluntary – you can choose whether or not to take part.

 Consent – by submitting, you agree your answers may be used for research and teaching improvement.

 No withdrawal – once submitted, answers cannot be withdrawn (because they are anonymous).

 Questions? Contact: vassolagari@gmail.com

 Full consent form: [View here](#)

* Indicates required question

1. "I have read the above information and consent to participate in this survey." *
- If you select "No," you will be directed to the end of the form.

Mark only one oval.

Yes, I consent *Skip to question 2*

No, I do not consent

Questionnaire

Background

(Knowledge & Experience)

2. Please indicate your prior (before starting the course) theoretical knowledge in * the following topics:

Mark only one oval per row.

	None	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Expert
3D recording (photogrammetry / laser scanning / SLS scanning)	<input type="radio"/>				
3D reconstruction/modeling (e.g. Blender, Meshlab)	<input type="radio"/>				
GIS	<input type="radio"/>				
Archaeological Sciences (archaeometrical / geophysical methods)	<input type="radio"/>				
Data Curation (FAIR principles, metadata, paradata)	<input type="radio"/>				

3. Please indicate your prior (before starting the course) practical experience in the * following topics:

Mark only one oval per row.

	None	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Expert
3D recording (photogrammetry / laser scanning / SLS scanning)	<input type="radio"/>				
3D reconstruction/modeling (e.g. Blender, Meshlab)	<input type="radio"/>				
GIS	<input type="radio"/>				
Archaeological Sciences (archaeometrical / geophysical methods)	<input type="radio"/>				
Data Curation (FAIR principles, metadata, paradata)	<input type="radio"/>				

Questionnaire

Learning Experience (Engagement / Usefulness / Effectiveness)

4. How useful were the following activities to your learning? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very useful	Useful	Neutral	Slightly useful	Not useful
Traditional lectures	<input type="radio"/>				
In-classroom discussions	<input type="radio"/>				
Digital examples (experience with online collections, databases, maps, 3D models, digital publications, VR/AR simulations)	<input type="radio"/>				
Tutorials (hands-on experience with certain techniques/tools)	<input type="radio"/>				
Essays with freedom to explore topics and techniques	<input type="radio"/>				

5. How engaging and helpful did you find the hands-on tutorials (photogrammetry, 3D reconstruction, 3D modeling) provided in the course? *

Mark only one oval.

- Very engaging
- Somewhat engaging
- Neutral
- Not very engaging
- Not engaging at all

6. The hands-on tutorials were not obligatory. To what extent did you return to them *
later on your own?

Mark only one oval.

- I completed all of them later (or during the class)
- I completed some of them later
- I looked at them briefly but did not complete them
- I did not work on them after class

7. If you did return to the tasks later, what motivated you to do so?

8. How engaging did you find the weekly discussion-point activity (reading and *
bringing discussion questions to class)

Mark only one oval.

- Very engaging
- Somewhat engaging
- Neutral
- Not very engaging
- Not engaging at all

9. How confident did you feel preparing discussion points at the beginning of the *
course compared to later?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very confident

10. What helped you engage more actively in the discussion-point activity over time?

11. The final essay followed an agent-based perspective where you were asked to devise your own research project (freedom to define every step: theme, research questions, structure). How difficult was this process for you? *

Mark only one oval.

- Very difficult
- Difficult
- Neutral
- Slightly difficult
- Not difficult

12. The final essay followed an agent-based perspective where you were asked to devise your own research project (freedom to define every step: theme, research questions, structure). How effective was this approach for your learning? *

Mark only one oval.

- Very effective
- Effective
- Neutral
- Slightly effective
- Not effective

Questionnaire

Applications and Skills / Aftermath

13. Have you used (or do you plan to use) the knowledge or skills from this course * in your own research or professional work?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, already using
- Yes, plan to use
- Not sure yet
- No

14. **If yes, please give an example (e.g. integrating photogrammetry in thesis, using GIS in the field , etc.):**

15. Did the course influence your choice of research topics, thesis/dissertation * direction, or professional path?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, significantly
- Yes, somewhat
- No

16. To what extent did the course help you develop the following skills? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly improved	Improved	Neutral	Limited	Not at all
Critical thinking	<input type="radio"/>				
Practical knowledge of digital tools	<input type="radio"/>				
Independent research skills	<input type="radio"/>				

Questionnaire

Reflection

17. What were the main challenges you faced in engaging with digital tools during the course (e.g. technical, conceptual, access, workload)?

18. How would you compare this digital/interactive pedagogy to more traditional teaching methods?

19. **What suggestions would you give to improve the course in the future?**

20. **Any additional comments on your overall experience?**

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